

The Opportunities for Timber Production in an Agroforestry System and the Supports Available in Ireland

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Silvopastoral agroforestry system (Photo: Teagasc)
Cattle grazing in a high pruned young oak woodland

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In Ireland, silvopasture integrates trees with livestock grazing, balancing timber production, biodiversity, and farm resilience while maintaining pasture productivity. This practice provides shade, shelter, and soil enrichment, benefiting both agriculture and the environment.

Silvopasture has existed for centuries but is now expanding due to government grants and growing farmer awareness. Key advantages include high-quality timber, fruit/nut yields, improved livestock welfare, carbon sequestration, and soil conservation. Trees reduce wind damage, mitigate flooding, and enhance water quality, supporting climate resilience.

Silvopasture practices requires careful species selection and management. Trees like oak, sycamore, cherry, and walnut thrive in wide spacings (400-1,000 trees/ha), allowing for continued grazing. Proper pruning ensures knot-free timber, with trees grown at least 6 meters straight before canopy expansion.

Site conditions are critical as well-drained, fertile soils promote growth, while factors like climate, frost, wind exposure, and topography influence success. Trees should be pit-planted, protected with shelters or fencing early in the establishment stage, and pruned every 2-3 years to maintain straight growth. But tree damage also depends on the type of breed livestock and livestock species affecting the woody perennial-livestock compatibility.

Irish farmers can access funding through the Agroforestry Scheme, Afforestation Scheme, and Woodland Improvement Scheme, covering planting, maintenance, and thinning. The Agroforestry scheme supports trees with food production on plots of at least 0.5 ha, with a minimum width of 20 m and 400 trees ha⁻¹. Eligible species include oak, sycamore, and cherry, with others considered. Once converted, land is classified as forest under the Forestry Act 2014. Grants offer €6,000- €8,555 per hectare (excluding fencing) and €829- €975 annually for 10 years.

Silvopasture is a sustainable land-use system that enhances timber production, livestock welfare, and conservation. With rising timber demand and strong policy support, it is becoming a key strategy in Irish agriculture.

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